

Panel Report

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Panel Title: Innovation & Research in Clinical Environments: Overcoming Challenges for the Future of Healthcare Powered by: Carebridge

MEI2024, 2nd Smart Health Innovation & Future Technologies Conference

KEDEA, Thessaloniki, 11th June 2024, 11:30-12:30.

Panellists:

Stelios Hadjidimitriou, PhD, Senior Researcher at Signal Processing & Biomedical Technology Unit, AUTH

Michael Dumas, Professor, Director of the 2nd Propaedeutic Internal Medicine Clinic of Ippokrateio General Hospital of Thessaloniki

Adriane Thrash, Managing Partner, Anthology Ventures

Apostolia Karabatea, R&D Project Manager, Gnomon Informatics SA

Chair: **Despoina Petsani**, Research and Innovation Project Manager, CAPTAIN Coach P.C., CareBridge project Coordinator

1. Introduction

The 5th International Conference on Medical Education Informatics (MEI2024) featured the SHIFT-HUB conference, the 2nd Smart Health Innovation & Future Technologies Conference, as a satellite event. This satellite event included a panel discussion titled "Innovation & Research in Clinical Environments: Overcoming Challenges for the Future of Healthcare," powered by Carebridge. The panel focused on various challenges and strategies related to the adoption of new technologies in clinical environments, with contributions from multiple stakeholders in the healthcare sector.

2. Panel Discussion Highlights

One of the primary challenges in innovation and research in clinical environments, acknowledged by all panellists, is resistance to change driven by concerns over workflow disruptions and the reliability of new technologies. This leads to reluctance among doctors and patients to adopt new technologies, especially when dealing with people with restricted digital literacy and when the benefits of the technology are still unclear. Financial constraints, including the high initial investment costs and ongoing maintenance expenses, as well as time constraints and inadequate human resources, further

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compound these barriers. From an entrepreneurial perspective, companies, especially start-ups, encounter additional hurdles such as time pressures to bring their solutions to the market, regulatory and budgetary resistance, and political challenges.

Balancing research time and market urgency is another critical aspect. Despite advances in technology for big data analysis and storing, leveraging real-world data and large-scale databases to enhance the robustness of results and develop AI tools remains a challenge. The situation in Greece is not favourable for the introduction of new technologies, as comprehensive databases in clinical environments are still lacking. As a result, there is often a gap between data collection and data processing and the attempt to involve new stakeholders is hindered by time constraints. Although successful examples exist, it is challenging to conduct the assessment, deal with the regulatory aspects and face people's reluctance at the same time. The differences in regulations and clinical workflows add an extra complexity.

All panellists underscored the importance of co-creation and patient involvement in research studies early enough in the study design. Research activities should be driven by the needs of patients and doctors, requiring close collaboration among all stakeholders. For the actual adoption and sustainability of solutions, the panel stressed the necessity of regulatory compliance, ongoing support, and measurable benefits in terms of both time and money for all involved. Introducing a research outcome to the market, especially in health and clinical care, involves overcoming significant regulatory hurdles. It is crucial for those running the business to have the core competencies to navigate these challenges. While innovation is encouraged among researchers, not all possess the skills and knowledge to bring their solution to the market.

Strategies for collaboration among stakeholders can help address some of these challenges. The panel advocated for improving communication and transparency, along with creating interdisciplinary research centres, to accelerate the integration of health-tech into the market. Co-creation involving all stakeholders and leveraging available tools for better collaboration between researchers and businesses is key. Clear communication from the outset should be a core strategy when developing an innovation to ensure the developed tools are useful for clinicians. A bottom-up approach, involving stakeholders at all levels early in the process, was supported to ensure robust development and widespread applicability.

3. Main Outcomes and Recommendations

The main barriers to innovation in clinical environments, as agreed upon by all panellists, stem from human resistance and regulatory obstacles in the health field. Key strategies for overcoming challenges in adopting new technologies in clinical environments include:

1. **Co-creation:** Engaging stakeholders early and continuously through co-creation is crucial. All panellists emphasized the importance of involving patients and doctors in the research process from the study design phase. Initiating research activities based on their needs and fostering close collaboration among all stakeholders ensures that the outcomes are relevant and more likely to be adopted.
2. **Improved Communication:** Ensuring transparency and collaboration among diverse teams is vital for success. Effective communication helps bridge gaps between researchers, clinicians, and business professionals, leading to better understanding and alignment of goals. Such strategy can mitigate resistance and navigate regulatory complexities, fostering a conducive environment for innovation in clinical settings.
3. **Interdisciplinary Research:** Establishing collaboration strategies to integrate various expertise in research is key to overcoming the complexities of health-tech integration. Creating

interdisciplinary research centres can accelerate the process by combining knowledge from different fields, fostering innovation, and addressing challenges from multiple perspectives.

4. **Focus on Real Needs:** Prioritizing needs and ensuring interoperability is essential for the successful implementation of new technologies. Research should be driven by the actual needs of patients and doctors, ensuring that the solutions developed are practical and beneficial. Leveraging real-world data and large-scale databases, despite the challenges, can enhance the robustness of AI tools and other innovations.
5. **Bottom-Up Approach:** Understanding dynamics at all levels through a bottom-up approach ensures robust development and widespread applicability. Involving stakeholders at all levels early in the process helps identify potential issues and adapt solutions to fit the specific contexts of different clinical environments. This approach promotes widespread adoption and sustainability of health-tech innovations.

4. Conclusion

The panel highlighted critical challenges and solutions in adopting new technologies in clinical environments. Emphasizing co-creation, improved communication, and interdisciplinary collaboration, the panellists provided valuable insights into overcoming resistance and ensuring the successful integration of innovative health technologies. This comprehensive approach underscores the importance of technology as a tool rather than the solution itself in advancing healthcare. Technology cannot transform healthcare without respective changes in behaviour and regulatory frameworks.